

Report from the mini-symposium

Studying the complexities of success in collaborative protected areas

A multi-stakeholder dialogue on the case of octopus closures and process-focused research

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Contributions

Emilie Lindkvist, Liz Drury O'Neill, Tim Daw, and Jineth Berrío-Martínez prepared the mini-symposium, Andrew Wamukota facilitated the mini-symposium and Rosemarie Mwaipopo moderated the panel discussion. Emilie, Liz, Tim and Rosemarie held oral presentations. Lorna Slade, Shauna Mahajan, Tanguy Nicholas and Tahiry Randrianjafimanana were the distinguished panelists. We thank and acknowledge the important contributions of the team, panelists and all the participants of the symposium as listed at the end of this report. Photo front page by Liz Drury O'Neill.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The OctoPINTS research project has over the last three years studied and explored stakeholders and rightsholders experiences and perceptions around the intervention of periodic reef closures of octopuses (or in some cases for all species). Periodic closures are increasingly implemented across the Western Indian Ocean (WIO) region. In only ten years after pilots in 2004, this intervention had been replicated more than 200 times. These closures are of particular interest to fisheries researchers and managers as they are locally led, can act as catalysts for co-management, and in most cases directly engage gender dynamics. Whether a closure is perceived as successful, depends on the diverse expectations and interests of different stakeholders, including managers, conservationists, fishers, local communities, exporters and traders.

The WIOMSA mini-symposium: *Studying the complexity of success in collaborative protected areas: a case of octopus closures in the WIO*, aimed to discuss the different types of research conducted by researchers and practitioners, and how it can be useful for informing the practice of supporting periodic octopus closures. The OctoPINTS project shared their findings having characterized their approach as being 'process-focused', and a distinguished panel of expert practitioners were invited to discuss the merits of different research approaches to inform practical conservation and management interventions.

What is process-focused research? Exemplifying the OctoPINTS point of view

After fieldwork in 2019, the OctoPINTS team recently returned to Zanzibar to share our findings with community members, NGOs and government representatives. We were fascinated by the reaction to our research approach. We received both positive responses and appreciation for getting at the 'real truth', however some questioned its relevance. We were curious to understand what was challenging about our research approach? How did it differ from other approaches? What role do these different approaches have for practice?

To distinguish our research approach, we labeled it as process-focused to emphasize a focus on understanding processes of how and why things unfold in contrast to indicator-focused for measuring indicators answering how much or what (Table 1). We applied a process-focused approach through three different methodologies.

First, through Liz's fieldwork where story circles, photo elicitation tasks and focus group discussions helped discover how various Zanzibari participants thought about the practice of closures and the activities around them (Fig. 2). Her findings showed a diversity of reasoning around what were successful outcomes and how they differed across social groups (e.g. men, women, footfishers, divers, and traders). Examples include the satisfaction of catching big octopus, the festivities at openings, or benefits for the community (e.g. roofing the mosque), but also concerns about poaching

and non-compliance. Participants shared various narratives around who was responsible, how it should be dealt with, and why poaching happens. Specifically processes around patrolling, fisher characteristics such as gender, gear, and people's acceptance of the closure mattered for poaching behavior.

Emilie took these findings to design an agent-based simulation model where individual octopuses, fishers with different gender and gear, and the reef area were represented (Fig. 3). We used the model to explore effects of e.g. initial levels of patrolling and poaching on closure outcomes such as average size and weight of octopuses in the different reef areas. We could observe how fishers' acceptance towards practicing closures changed over time as poaching levels changed, or big octopuses were caught.

As expected, the modeling raised many new interesting questions for us. Rose arranged for a final field trip to investigate these questions further with social mapping, i.e., moving with the people to see who's participating in what action and why. From an anthropologist's perspective she could perceive the closure as a value system where the relative autonomy of groups, beyond gender, was key. Each group had different ideas on what a closure is, and had different values. In this way, it communicated a system of power relations. Her conclusion was that the bigger challenge to obtain success seemed to be negotiating between these groups with very different value systems.

Table 1. Characteristics of process-focused versus indicator-focused research approaches.

Process-focused approach	Indicator-focused approach
<p>Characterized as qualitative, exploratory, open-ended or semi-structured participatory research, in an interpretive tradition with a focus on understanding why? and how?</p> <p>The more open-ended fieldwork approaches specifically allows for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> let research participants define what aspects of a topic is relevant to speak about discovery of how research participants reason about how and why things happen discovery of people's feelings and perceptions <p>The agent-based modeling specifically allows for:</p>	<p>Characterized as quantitative, non-exploratory, measurements of indicators, with a focus on understanding what? or how much?</p> <p>Allows for</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> targeted questions and/or to measure pre-determined indicators rigorous testing and demonstration of impact for learning and presenting to funders ensuring that data is collected on all variables of interest to the researchers or other stakeholders (e.g. government agencies, funders)

<ul style="list-style-type: none">● investigating how agent's interactions with each other and with their environment affect outcomes of an intervention● investigate how contextual changes (e.g. new policies, effects of climate change) affects outcomes	
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Panel discussions

What are the successful outcomes of a closure from your perspective?

Echoing earlier discussions from our WIOMSA 2019 special session, 'success' of an intervention can be understood in various ways, and different stakeholders may have different criteria for success. Community members may pay heed to different aspects such as relational gains or losses, possibly missed by standard indicators. Our panel agreed that what determines success is variable between people, hence co-developing initiatives to capture what is important to people in the communities, and learning together becomes key. Ultimately, if the majority of people feel positively about an intervention this may empower a community towards opportunities for progress in other forms of collaborative conservation or other initiatives.

What kind of research do you think would help us understand what are successful outcomes of closures? Why?

We discussed and agreed on the importance of both indicator- and process-focused research. Still, most publications in the WIO on octopus closures are currently more indicator-focused (Fig. 4). Our panelists echoed this, and agreed that more process-focused research could help to better understand why things go well or why not, to learn and adapt strategies over time.

While any practitioner is always gaining deeper knowledge and understanding of each of their cases, these types of more in-depth open-ended or modeling initiatives would be in addition to this constant learning process. However, issues remain before this will be possible. Regarding the more open-ended fieldwork approach, questions remain around who should be undertaking this research? External academics, on-the-ground practitioners, or even community members? Practitioners sometimes lack skills and time for in-depth reflection, while academics can lack familiarity with the situation and priorities on the ground. Academics can provide an outsider perspective and appropriate methodology, but NGOs are more likely to understand, use, and target research to practical challenges if they are responsible themselves.

However, neither the funders of NGOs nor the structures of NGOs currently support the considerable time needed for this type of research and primarily want quantifiable results measuring impact (i.e. indicator-focused). This change could be facilitated by funders being open to more process-focused research to feed into the projects they finance. In addition, research tends to be initiated by academics in response to funding opportunities. Facilitating ways for community members and practitioners to invite academic collaborations would be an interesting way forward to balance whose questions get researched.

After the sessions, in preparation for a special issue of the WIOMSA magazine, the OctoPINTS project and panelists prepared a short piece summarizing our session and agreed on some suggestions for the Ocean Decade based on our discussions (Box 1).

Box 1. We propose bringing in more **process-focused open-ended research** in collaboration between **practitioners, policy and academia** to:

- allow communities and other local stakeholders to **co-design the framing of research**, avoiding biases based on assumptions or pre-conceptions by outsiders or non-locals
- provide opportunity for community members, practitioners, researchers and funders to **learn together to generate new ideas for action** to support community-led fisheries management and conservation
- allow for more **nuanced and diverse perspectives** on the multiple ways rights- and stakeholders can perceive an initiative as **'successful'**
- accounting for people's feelings and **perceptions as important motivators in human action**
- foster the use of diverse methods or mixed-methods approaches including **novel tools** that allow **integrating** different types of **knowledge**

MINI-SYMPOSIUM INTRODUCTION

As submitted as a proposal to the WIOMSA organizers.

Motivation of topic

Following on a special session run at the WIOMSA Symposium 2019 the OctoPINTS research project, this mini-symposium sets out to conclude our work, and is inspired by the **methodological approaches** adopted over the past three years. In the 2019 session, OctoPINTS, together with practitioners and academics, explored diverse perspectives on what **success** meant in the context of periodic octopus closures across the WIO. The subsequent OctoPINTS research has explored both how Zanzibari communities perceive the success of community-based octopus closures as well as

factors that lead to more or less successful outcomes. Octopus closures is thus a case with which to explore the social and ecological **complexity of small-scale fishery interventions** including negotiations around gendered differences and **social differentiation** within and between communities.

Our work combines **agent-based modeling** and **qualitative participatory research**. Our approach focused on tracing the processes through which implementation of a protected area led to different outcomes and how these fed back into management decisions. In this session we aim to feedback the findings of this 'process-focused' approach and create space for an open discussion on to what extent process-focused research can support practical conservation and management actions by organizations and individuals.

Novelty and impact of the topic

Scientific and development approaches to collaborative marine management are typically '**indicator-focused**'. This means they measure specific variables (often quantitatively), such as catch rates or income levels, that are chosen as indicators of desired outcomes of management. However, such variables are less useful for understanding why such outcomes evolved or for understanding how future interventions could contribute to better outcomes. In contrast, '**process-focused**' approaches are concerned with understanding **how and why particular outcomes emerge based on (often qualitative) understandings of social, ecological and social-ecological cause and effect relationships**. We will explore whether such an approach can address challenges facing management interventions, coupled with multiple interests and understandings. The impact of such a methodological approach will be discussed with those in the session, including the strengths, pitfalls and practicalities of process-focused mixed-method research in a collaborative protected area setting.

Mini-symposium agenda 16:00-17:40

The structure will involve a series of talks from project members followed by a panel with speakers from Mwambao Coastal Community Network, Blue Ventures, Fauna & Flora International and the World Wildlife Foundation.

- 16:00 Welcome by Andrew Wamukota & Rosemarie Wamukota
- 16:05 Round of introductions (name and organization of those in the room and online)
- 16:10 Introduction by Tim Daw. What is the OctoPINTS project and why are we here?
- 16:20 Talk 1 by Emilie Lindkvist: "*Agent-based modeling for understanding dynamics of octopus closures*".
- 16:30 Talk 2 by Elizabeth Drury O'Neill: "*Liz's approach to fieldwork*"
- 16:45 Talk 3 by Rosemarie Mwaipopo: "*Communities and Closures*"
- 16:55 QnA on presentations from audience
- 17:00 BREAK - The panel takes a seat

- 17:05 Introduction of panelists
17:10 Panel discussion hosted by Rosemarie Mwaipopo
17:35 Reflections and thank you
17:40 END

Overview of questions to the panelists

Prepared questions for the panelists, questions as posed in session - see transcript

1. What is your freshest thought having heard the presentations and discussions so far?
2. From your perspective, what is a 'successful' closure intervention? Do you know what leads to successful outcomes?
3. What kinds of research can help you understand how to achieve success?
4. Do you recognize the distinction between process-focused and indicator-focused research? Why? How is each useful or not for community-based conservation interventions?
5. Is open-ended research (rather than going after specific questions) useful for your work?
6. Is research that emphasizes community members' own subjective reality (rather measuring an objective truth) useful for your work?
7. What kind of research do we need more of to inform practical conservation?
8. Is there anything you would like to add that we have not highlighted so far?
- 1.

A summary of the answers can be found in the executive summary, detailed answers as transcribed see **Part 2** further down.

Panelists

Lorna Slade - MWAMBAO

Technical Advisor, co-founder of MWAMBAO Coastal community network, Tanzania. <https://mwambao.or.tz/>. Raised in Kenya, Lorna has a long history of work in environmental conservation and development issues. She is a strong proponent of the community's role and voice in management of natural resources and believes in the power of participatory video in making a difference. Trained as an ecologist and in participatory video methodology, she is committed to building the Mwambao network.

Shauna Mahajan - World Wildlife Foundation

Lead Social Scientist, Global Science, Geographic focus in Coastal East Africa.

<https://www.worldwildlife.org/>. Shauna is committed to developing inclusive and holistic solutions to conservation problems. With an interdisciplinary background in resilience thinking, environment, and development, her work and research focuses broadly on the social dimensions of conservation, with a special focus on coastal communities. At WWF, Shauna develops and tests methods for conservation strategy development and evaluation, while also researching the science of decision-making, and the natural resource governance systems that enable positive social and ecological outcomes from conservation.

Tahiry Randrianjafimanana - Blue Ventures

National Technical Advisor for Fisheries management and Marine Protected areas, Antananarivo, Madagascar. <https://blueventures.org/>. Tahiry leads the implementation of the fisheries programme strategies in the bay of Tsimipaika, including fisheries monitoring, management and research. He is particularly interested in studying ecosystem services provided by mangrove forests and coral reefs, and he is passionate about finding sustainable solutions to the overfishing and increasing resilience of communities and ecosystems to climate change.

Tanguy Nicolas - Fauna & Flora International

Marine Technical Specialist for Africa <https://www.fauna-flora.org/>. Initially working in non-emergency humanitarian contexts and rural development, he gradually set foot at the interface between natural resources management and local economic development, particularly in coastal and marine areas. His work experience in Africa has mainly focussed in Central Africa and Western Indian Ocean regions, but he has also worked with microfinance in France with economically-marginalized individuals. Tanguy strongly believes individual and collective empowerment through different tools are key to bring about positive changes for people and nature.

Expected outputs of the mini-symposium

A perspective piece on indicators vs. process focused approaches, and tie this into viewpoints on what defines successful small-scale fishery interventions, submitted by April 2023. The piece will include outcomes from this symposium as well as results from our WIOMSA 2019 Special Session on “Gathering Experiences of Octopus Closures in the WIO region: Towards a synthesis of actors, interactions and outcomes”. This mini-symposium further creates an opportunity for the network of researchers and practitioners to reconnect around the topic of closures, success, and co-management.

MINI-SYMPOSIUM: A MULTI-STAKEHOLDER DIALOGUE

In this section, we present a full overview of the talks held and then transcripts from our panel discussions and audience questions.

Part 1 OctoPINTS presentations

Introductory Talk: Background by Tim Daw

The OctoPINTS project has a number of academic partners from Stockholm University, but also Rose from University of Dar es Salaam and Andrew from Pwani University. In terms of non academic partners and collaborators, we have been learning and developing the research with MWAMBAO and also learning from the experience of Blue Ventures and Fauna & Flora International (FFI), among others that have participated in our expert workshops.

OctoPINTS is interested in the 'success' of octopus closures. We wanted to dig into this idea of success in terms of short and long term outcomes, but also by the benefits and perceptions that accrue to different groups within the communities, for example, based on gender.

At WIOMSA 2019, at the start of the project, we had a full day session together with FFI, where we had a really interesting collection of people working with closures and similar interventions. Key outcomes were the diversity of understandings of success in terms of ecological or financial or social or empowerment, and that different organizations and institutions conceptualize success in different ways.

The workshop also identified some frontiers for research, in terms of the need to look at gender and social differentiation, how different people benefit from and are affected by closures, ecological effects of closures on other species beyond octopus, as different factors influencing success.

In the OctoPINTS project we were looking at that very much from the community's perspective, but did not specifically study the ecological effects. However participants in our fieldwork did raise some reflections on this.

Our project combines different types of methodologies: qualitative social science fieldwork, in Zanzibar, however not as much as we had planned because of COVID. We also draw on expert elicitation from different organizations and practitioners working with closures.

The qualitative insights from how an octopus closure is perceived by the community, and the different activities around closures feeds into agent-based computer modeling. Emilie will talk about how we model individual agents who make decisions, and the decisions they make have effects on how the system evolves.

Our focus is on understanding why things happen and how things happen. We try to understand the processes that are underlying the outcomes from a given intervention by using qualitative knowledge and feeding into agent-based computer simulations. We were trying that out as a tool for having a better understanding of the mechanisms of it, the processes that are happening in complex situations, but where there is a limited amount of data availability.

Process-focused research

In characterizing our research approach, we can think of it as being this process-focused as in on these questions of why and how. For instance, why do people comply or not? And in our fieldwork, it also led to an approach which has quite open questions. So you will see in Liz's data, she asked participants questions like tell me about your experience within the closure, rather than narrow targeted questions.

Based on that assumption of what we think is important within the system. Much of our data that we have drawn was qualitative. And we were also interested in stories from people's own perspective, because in trying to understand how agents should make decisions in the model, it is important to understand the worlds of individual people, their own experiences and interpretations of the world.

Indicator-focused research

And we can contrast process-focused research with a different approach that is more focused on indicators and which focuses on measuring how much of things are happening. So for example, how many poaching events are there? , looking for quantitative indicators, or answering predetermined questions. Surveys, for example, on catches and income, how is your income affected by the closure? based on a previous understanding that income is the key variable. These kinds of approaches can often but they do not have to be quantitative, and they are more focused on objectively measuring the world, then understanding the world through people's own perspectives.

Process focused (OctoPINTS)- WHY? / HOW?	Indicator focused research - WHAT? / HOW MUCH?
Focussed on why things happen (process) “why do people comply or not?”	Focussed on measuring what happens (indicators) “how many poaching events?”
Open questions “tell me about your experience with the closure?”	Predetermined questions “how is your income affected by the closure?”
Often qualitative	Often quantitative
Stories from people’s own perspective	Objective measurements

Why this dichotomy?

To help with the conversation, we caricature the different kinds of research as being more process-focused or indicator-focus. And we can discuss whether that classification is useful or not to try and see how the OctoPINTS process-focused research fits in with other research happening in the region.

Rapid literature scan on process vs. indicator-based research of octopus closures in the WIO

We did a short literature scan to look at the purpose and the methods that have been used to study up octopus closures in the WIO. Keyword searches included “octopus closures” and “Locally Managed Marine Areas” in the WIO in Google Scholar, Stockholm library databases, publications, WIOMSA and African journals and the TAFIRI publications, and some snowballing.

By reviewing the abstract, methods and conclusions, we quickly classified the documents into either being indicator-based when the purpose focuses on the what or how much or

process-based when they address the why or how. We found and reviewed 40 documents and categorized them in this way.

We found that most studies were focused on reporting or assessing the impact of closures before and after, rather than focusing on explicitly why or how certain outcomes evolved. There was also not very much focus on social differentiation, for example, gender differences. In that way, the type of research that we do is a little bit different to much of the research that is happening on this topic in the WIO region.

The methods “landscape” of octopus closures in the WIO

Feedback sessions Zanzibar, 2022

In July, we went back to Zanzibar, we had a series of workshops and feedback sessions with communities, as well as an open feedback session to stakeholders in Stone Town (Lindkvist et al 2022). We shared our qualitative work through fictive stories, and we combined them into a [play script](#) that we were able to act out to the community members that had been part of the research. And we found that these stories, this qualitative storytelling really resonated with people. And it also helped to highlight some of the key social dimensions of the closure model and supported some interesting discussions.

In terms of our research methodology being more open, more inductive, was appreciated by some stakeholders; and some NGOs thought it was a useful approach to try and find out from the community's perspective, what were the main issues without being guided by a preconceptions of what the main issues that we should be asking about. However, some organizations and some

government representatives were not so convinced by that open inductive research and felt that that missed important topics that were assumed to be important, for example, health as we did not explicitly ask about health. And because health did not emerge when we asked people about their relationship with closures, we did not get data on that. So, they felt it was missing.

It was interesting to see how this kind of process-based, open ended, interpretive methodology landed with different stakeholders. These mixed results partly inspired this mini-symposium. Here, we want to discuss the different research approaches and how they can or cannot be useful in support of octopus closures and conservation actions in the region. The overarching question we are asking today is:

“Can process-based research inform community based conservation practice?”

Next, we will hear about the OctoPINTS methods and results from Emilie, Liz, and Rose.

Talk 1 by Emilie Lindkvist: Causal complexities in small-scale fisheries: An agent-based modeling approach for understanding dynamics of periodic octopus closures

Emilie presented the agent-based modeling, as another way to investigate why and how certain outcomes may arise from implementing the closure model. The aim was to give a sense of what the model can contribute with, rather than model details. The model will be publicly available in the future open source, as well as the software needed to run the model.

The Objectives

The objective of the modeling component of the OctoPINTS project is to understand why and how outcomes of the closure model may unfold over time depending on different scenarios. **A scenario can be**, for example, a certain set of closure design rules, a specific community context, or changing ecological or biological factors. By simulating different scenarios, we also observe results on **how outcomes may change** depending on which scenario we study. We use the model to explore this in a more theoretical scientific sense in trying to understand general processes around closures and how they interact, but also the aim is for people to learn and reason about, for example, what a successful closure can be and what influences the success.

The Methodology

As an entry point this component is the agent-based modeling. This tool is well-known for its ability to represent individuals such as fishers or octopuses in a more or less realistic way and modeling the behavior and actions of those individuals. We took a more unconventional way of designing the

model, that is an approach used for instance in anthropology, which is - that instead of using numbers and using the model to predict outcomes – we design the model based on the analysis of Liz’s qualitative fieldwork data and compare the outcomes to narratives of her work. We combine this with literature and expert interviews on octopus biology for modeling aspects of their growth and reproduction as well as movement behaviors, and build on expert workshops for selecting interesting scenarios. Through the link with Liz’s fieldwork naturally include gender lens even in this work.

Model design

In the model we represent different social groups such as **women footfishers**, **male skin divers**, and **incoming fishers** (who are those that do not normally fish octopus but are attracted to the openings).

These social groups have variables that describe their perceptions of the closure, and other personal attributes. **Acceptance** is the key variable that determines if they perceive the closure intervention as successful or not. Acceptance of the closure of a social agent (or actor) will increase if they get big octopuses at the openings; and it also increases because of the festive feelings. Acceptance will decrease if poachers are not caught or do not pay their fines. They also have a **propensity to comply** which is affected by the acceptance of the closure, the level of patrolling, and also which social group they belong to. **Octopuses** in the model can grow, move, reproduce, migrate and die. These behaviors are not included in this symposium talk.

Model graphical interface. The figures of the model looking at the reef, and the closure area to the right, with guards in black patrolling the closure. 1) Top panel: day 1 of the closure being put in place. 2) Middle panel: day 83 just before opening and at high tide (no women can fish) - an aggregation of octopuses in the closure area. 3) Bottom panel: Opening day.

Simulated scenarios

Some examples of scenarios it is possible to explore with the model are e.g., closure design rules with respect to closure cycles (days open, days closed), closure size, or different entry rules.

Scenarios it is possible to simulate with the model.

Findings for landings across social groups and scenarios

First let's look at some outcomes of the different scenarios in the figure below..

Figure. Different scenarios (along the x-axis) with respect to kilos landed at openings by different fisher groups (at the y-axis). The Baseline scenario is what we compare the others too. The Incoming means three times as many fishers as normally would come to the opening – this decreases that average kg caught quite drastically. Women 1st means women enter alone the first day and the others are allowed the next day which secures their catches. Lack of funds means they are running out of money for patrolling, affecting all fishers. Octopuses move

deep, is a phenomenon described in literature where the movement of people scare off the octopuses outward to deeper waters, and as the graph shows the effect is affecting foot fishers negatively as their catches go down.

Findings: How and why did outcomes change?

Here I give two examples of the mechanism-based analysis of the model, it is a way of investigating the model over time to see why certain outcomes arise. These explanations are at the heart of this modeling approach.

Women enter 1st. Women get higher catches and bigger octopus leads to → higher overall satisfaction in the community because more landings within the community, which leads to → less poaching over time which leads to → that the landings at openings increase over time.

Lack of funds for patrolling. patrolling costs too high which leads to → the village cannot afford sufficient patrolling which leads to → people taking from the closure which leads to → poachers not being caught nor paying fines which leads to → acceptance of the closure model goes down which leads to → less benefits for all from closure.

This closed the presentation of the model. This is work in progress and the model scenarios are still to be decided for publications, however, any scenario can be modeled in the free open access version of the model that will be available soon at www.comses.net.

Talk 2 by Elizabeth (Liz) Drury O'Neill: Liz's approach to the fieldwork in the OctoPINTS project

My approach can be defined with a couple of different words. It was overall qualitative, and empirically based. It was explorative, subjective, focused on nuances, diversity, and disaggregation. Objective reality for me cannot really be captured and the researcher and subject influence each other. Truth was what is authentic to the place and to the people one is researching with. The questions I was most interested in were the How and the Why questions.

This type of approach aligns with the way of doing science called interpretivism, or an interpretive paradigm. And this is based on the idea that reality is shaped by social contexts and social experiences, rather than being singular or objective. So the best way to study reality, or understand it is through the interpretations of research participants within their own context. My work was then based on the perspectives of the fieldwork participants, and they were able to define “the problem” in their own system, from their own point of view.

I used this approach for a couple of reasons. The first was kind of personal for the Zanzibar context, which is highly researched, especially in terms of Marine Science. I wanted to be as collaborative as possible, and have the research method as interactive rather than extractive. I wanted to prioritize the voices of those within the system directly impacted by marine protected areas or closures. Secondly, in terms of project interests, we wanted to be open, and explorative in our understanding of what octopus closures were, and how they impact different people. If we took such an open approach, then research could be directed by participants. Additionally, what Emily was going to model could be also influenced by them. And thirdly, in terms of academia, there is a gap around the kind of social subjective implications of marine protected areas, especially from the viewpoints of those beyond fishermen. Exploring the differential impacts of closures or protected areas, as defined by primary stakeholders. So, there is a need to complement monitoring and evaluation with this type of more open qualitative storied research process.

Data collection

In 2019, I met with about 70 participants. We only got to go once to Zanzibar because of COVID 19. We worked with fisherwomen, fishermen, skin divers (free divers), traderwomen who made soup and fried octopus, traders who sold local or to export, fisheries committees and village leaders. We worked at three sites in Unguja and Pemba, and used three different methods over the course of a week on three different days at each site. We met with each participant group type individually. The first method I used was **story circles**. This method comes from theater, and it involves people sitting in a circle, one storyteller is given the floor for five minutes or a designated time and the rest need to actively listen to them share their story. You just provide the participants with a theme and a story structure. This method allowed me to take a backseat, and it kind of centered on participants' experiences with me as a listener, taking the heat off the foreign researcher. I also thought it would be interesting to see what they wanted to tell me on this first interaction. On the second day, I met with participants and we did **photo elicitation tasks**. These come from anthropology and basically involve looking at images, photos, art pieces etc. They can come from the interviewer or the participants. You talk about the art and elicit interpretations from participants. I chose this method because it was fun. It is not an interview, and again, it took the focus off me as the foreign researcher. It also helped people to remember different aspects of the closures that had already happened in the past. I found, when we talked about the pictures, it was easier to get some more emotional accounts of what had happened. It was also easier to chat about more sensitive subjects like participation dynamics. The last day I met with people, we did **focus groups**, this is just where a researcher assembles some participants together, a select group, and facilitates the discussion between them. Again the researcher is not at the center of the stage. You talk about a specific issue or topic, we had some specific questions about compliance and closure impacts, because of the interest of the collaborating NGO, and of the project itself.

Analysis

I analyzed the transcripts, both inductively and deductively. According to the two different papers I wrote, or that currently I am writing for OctoPINTS. I used a software called MAXQDA. With this programme you basically bring all of your transcripts into the software, and you can use the programme to go through them and code for different themes or using a specific framework.

Results

I have some short results for the two papers that I am writing, one is about compliance, because people talked a lot about compliance, especially in the story circle. The second is about wellbeing, because people naturally frame the impacts and the benefits around the various wellbeing dimensions, both from an individual point of view, collectively, and in terms of nature itself.

In the [compliance paper "Compliance, Complexity and Cephalopods- Disaggregated Responses to Participatory Marine Conservation & Management, In Review"](#), I drew on two sociological frameworks that also use cognitive sciences, and anthropology.

Some quick patterns in and across the participant groups were: people's knowledge of the marine environment and the need for protecting it meant they were ready to uphold the laws and endorse the process - this convincing logic supports the relationship of local ecological knowledge, or LEK to compliance motivation, which you see in a lot of other cases. There was very little outright resistance only in one site that had a long complicated history of Western led conservation projects and a clear expectation of what *mradi* or project in kiswahili meant i.e. the direct benefits that they could or should get. One of the outliers to the previous pattern was presented by divers, the skin divers, who were more inclined to exhibit the most dynamic responses. So, they changed their responses through the methods and according to the different situation they were talking about. But most commonly, they had a "keep them happy" kind of attitude towards authorities, and a clear reluctance towards the rules or authorities, which translated largely into blaming migrants, fishing migrants as the free riders. Thus, meaning that it was futile to follow the rules, "why preserve for guests to come and take?". So, these types of responses typically lead to non compliant outcomes according to the theory.

It was men that were blatantly blamed for rule breaking across all sites, and by most groups. It was female groups, so traderwomen and fisherwomen, that tended to be most fixed in their positions to the rules and rule breaking throughout fieldwork. The traderwomen's high commitment to the process was associated with quite a strong moral opposition to breaking the rules based on necessity, meaning if you morally justify rule breaking due to the fact that you are poor. This dynamic was also seen with fisherwomen, they were also really committed. But this commitment, often translated into moral justifications around rule breaking, supporting the idea that following the rules can be futile, it can not be worth it, because of the free riding men, especially skin divers.

In two sites, we see a lack of autonomy, meaning the legitimacy of the state to intervene was almost completely unchallenged. In fact, the involvement of the state was directly called for many times, especially in the Pemba sites, and amongst mainly the male groups, not in Unguja.

Ultimately, you could say at the general level, the intervention was a support system, signaling a likelihood of future compliance, however, although groups were outwardly compliant, the interpretive approach helped us to see the diverse and dynamic responses by groups, indicating on which basis and through which logics compliance behavior was condoned, or legitimated.

For the wellbeing paper “Multidimensional human wellbeing in Periodic Octopus Closures, *In Review*” I used the social well being framework, which looks at subjective, material and relational dimensions of human wellbeing. So, universally across most groups, the benefits were the big and abundant octopus landings, the fact that one can celebrate and feel festive at the opening events, and income from selling that can go to individuals, but also collectively to the community for community related projects. Universally felt losses included the conflicts that people had in their relationships and amongst the community around poaching, and also the direct loss of octopus because of poaching.

If we look at skin divers, they felt they lost access to the octopus fishery as the main octopus fishers in the system. And that meant a reduction in their income. They also had some issues because of all the conflicts and the blame that came their way - so their relations were negatively impacted. Traderwomen felt included in the process. They felt that the tools and procedures provided by the closure, which I labeled market organization, allowed them to have more fairness and justice in the process. They were also able to meet the educational needs of their kids a little better, like through buying school books, uniforms. However, one of the only negative impacts was the prices, which they felt were a bit low, and were unfairly decided. Fisherwomen could now meet their daily needs a little better and also felt included in the process. Just like traderwomen, they were better able to meet the educational needs of their kids. However, the conflicts around poaching, the fighting in the community really negatively impacted them. Fishermen felt that they had now gained access to a fishery that they were not really using before, because they are the type of fishers normally fishing on boats with other gears and of other species. However, they felt prices were too low. And some felt that their access to other fisheries were impacted by the positions of the closure itself. Tradermen felt harvests had definitely increased (in abundance and/or sizes); however, the illegal buying and selling at opening events was negatively impacting them. They felt that they lost access to the huge amount of octopus products that they needed to export and to meet hotel or tourism demand in Unguja.

Talk 3 by Rosemarie Mwaipopo: Communities and Closures

Transcript done by Otter.ai, of Rose's presentation edited by Emilie & Jineth.

Mine is also a very brief presentation, and I am talking about some of the findings that I found in the fieldwork. And basically, my part of the project was coming in with a plurally cultural, social anthropological point of view. And in summary from the findings, what I got, which I do add to the project is from the people themselves, the participants is how they actually talk about closures. And, you can see how, to them, a closure is a value system. It is a system that they were communicating, it was solicited, not that they have not experienced it from before, but it was something to be solicited and to be shared across a community of diverse entities, persons and individuals. And from the discussion, you could see that they talk of closure as an intervention that actually establishes patterns, a certain system of relationships, but also a relationship that is geared towards a particular cause.

What we are trying to see what is this thing we call the "success" of a closure. And then, the other thing that I could tell from the people from the three communities that we were visiting, is that this closure actually, is to deal with the relative autonomy of groups, that diverse groups in these communities. And each group has different ideas on what a closure is, and has different values, but also it communicates a system of power relations.

So, similar to what Liz was saying is that you find it coming across the first two weeks that you talked with the communities. And the other thing that also summarizes their understanding of a closure, and what it would lead to success is that it is very important also to see how is this? How can we negotiate the involvement of different people, of different values and different power systems to make what is called "a successful closure". And therefore, the objective was the same to understand why and how people become involved in closures, and how through these reasons, that actually determined their level and nature of participation.

Now, in terms of methodology, in addition to what Liz has presented, I also did some social mapping. And that social mapping is moving with the people to see who is participating in what action and why. And in that way, also, even when we were talking about, you know, with the women, you actually talk about gender and disaggregation, not necessarily between male and female, but also within female groups. And what we found is that there are so many differences and the differences in value even within different categories of females. So, it is not simply about females, talking about male divers, but it is also between females talking about different groups of females, also, some of them not complying, some of them thinking that the closure was a good thing.

Now, in terms of findings, some of the things that we were coming across is this debate about compliance, what is compliance? compliance seems, it was communicated as if it was a normative sort of saying something that one is made to accept, one is made to follow certain rules. But to them, what was probably coming across that would be necessary to think of is consent, consent agreeing, and therefore, also taking responsibility, committed responsibility, and consent to them is, you could see how it actually attracts and probably maintains the participation. So, we found that they were trying to say that here we are, people have very different values, there are women who do certain things within the same area. But, they would not comply, because they did not consent to closure

rules. But, there are other women in other communities where they would, let's say, practice seaweed farming, but they would probably adhere to the rules because they had consented to what the closures would have meant to them.

Now, when it comes to our study, what do these debates on **consent** and **compliance** mean to resource marine resource management? What we could see is that it is very important now to understand what are the factors informing consent, the processes? One of the things is what values do they give to this closure process, octopus closures? But, the other thing is also how do the communities interpret the legitimacy of the process? And in the discussion, you could see, actually, how do they come to agree to conform, to comply with the rules? That is very, very different. Then, the other thing is also the meaning of the closures. In what sense? What does closure communicate to them? material gains, but to them, the most important thing that we were coming across were the relation of gains.

For example, in some communities, you can actually tell that people do understand and have experienced that closures up to a certain point can actually lead to a very beautiful harvest of octopus. But, when it comes to opening time, what do they gain? The three days of opening time, the rush thing and therefore, the distribution of gains although quite meaningful, but a quite an event, the people who can gain more are probably the men and some women, some traders and what the other people you would see gaining vary quite a small amount, but still they do understand that probably closure, after a certain point do have a certain benefit to the community. And, therefore what was coming across is that social aspects, the social aspect negotiation, how do you converge the relative autonomy of groups to consent to a particular process that leads to a successful closure?

And therefore, the anthropological part, this part of the study also brings in a lot of methodological reflections, and one is about the rulemaking as a whole the process leading to closures, and how we do manage differences within and without the community, but also how we understand how people think of the aftermath of closures there, access when and how, but also things like material gains, like the octopus market, there was a lot of issues to do with, why are we made to sell our octopus in a certain point? Why are not we being asked to probably contribute to how octopus marketing even on opening day should be actually done? So, my contribution to the project was that we start from what the people are trying to say, the value system that they say, but also how they think, negotiating with it between these different groups with very, very different value systems will be probably more important to the success of what we call "the success of a closure".

Thank you very much for listening.

[End of Rose Mawaipopo's talk]

Part 2 Open floor and panel discussion

QnA to the speakers from the audience (transcripts)

Speaker 1 (question from the audience)

I am just curious you know, in terms of public engagement and getting the communities to understand the science behind it, how was the process? How did you get them to understand the intervention that you're trying to get a product? It's not specific to any presenter.

Andrew Wamukota 00:08

The question was not specific to anybody. So, I hope you guys that are joining us from Stockholm, we can be able to listen to the questions.

Tim Daw 00:22

Hi, from Stockholm, can you hear us? I can hear you. Thanks. Thanks a lot for the question. So, it was mentioned briefly in my presentation that we conducted a feedback visit to share the findings with both within the communities and also with different stakeholders at a workshop in Stone Town. So firstly, I think the objective of the OctoPINTS project is to try studying what's going on in partnership with organizations who are doing work, supporting the closures. So the OctoPINTS project is a research project, our objective is not to convince people about the closure, or the value of closure or sort of persuade people. So, it's a research project that we hope, through our kind of dialogue and partnership with organizations who have that mandate and responsibility to help understand the situation. So, that was the one thing I would say. And the other thing we wanted to say is, just to share in terms of how we shared the information with the community members during our feedback sessions. Because especially Liz's fieldwork was about sort of drawing out stories from different people's perspectives, that fed very conveniently into a mode of sharing in terms of sharing stories. So as one thing that we really found resonated a lot with the community members was we had the stories, we had them put together into a small play, like a sketch, so they could, and so that voices from the field work would come back out and be played out in a sort of dramatic form in the meeting. So it was so people could really kind of hear the different voices that were in discussion with one another that came through in the field work. And that was one, I think we all reflected, that was one methodology of feeding back and stimulating those conversations and bringing up some of these negotiations that Dr. Rose was talking about within the discussions with committee members.

Andrew Wamukota 02:47

Thank you Tim for that. There is another question.

Speaker 2 02:50 (question from the audience)

Thank you. Mine is I just wanted to know whether there was any impact on income of participants in the octopus fishery. As a result of these closures. This I asked in light of one presentation we had this morning, where the researcher was saying that MPAs do not necessarily produce benefits for the communities involved. So these closures have any impact on the income of participants.

Andrew Wamukota 03:28

Lorna would like to respond to that.

Lorna Slade 03:37

Thank you. I don't think this was part of the topic that OctoPINTS were researching. But I can just say from my point of view that there is an economic benefit that I don't want to go into a lot of detail now that involves a levy, which is placed on the octopus that they try to sell. And that money goes back to help patrol and also links to community development projects. Every community has their own arrangement. Thank you

Andrew Wamukota 04:10

Thank you for that Lorna, I don't know if the question that you have is very burning, or we can roll it over to the panel discussion of this session. But if it is, if it's burning, we can go ahead with that.

Speaker 3 04:33 (question from the audience)

Thank you. Yes, very, very fast question. Thank you to all the presenters. So, as some of the presenters were saying, this is a research project. I would like to know if there is a component of researching on the ecological impact, mostly related to the openings. Sometimes there's so much pressure, so many people are bursting at the same time. Is the project looking at some of those issues?

Andrew Wamukota 05:02

Thank you for that. Lorna will talk about that.

Lorna Slade 05:11

Thank you. Again, that wasn't part of the research question. But, it is something that we do monitor in areas of the closures. So, we do in-water biological monitoring, looking at the substrate and looking at indicator species. So it's something that we are... Of course, these things are not things that they pick up very easily over a short period of time. But over a long period of time, we have seen some improvement in fish, for example, fish numbers and diversity in size.

I agree with you in that, there is a lot of trampling pressure at the time of opening, and you find many people who have never fished an octopus in their life. So, they decide that they want to come in on the opening day. I think in Rodrigues, they found an impact of trampling at the opening time, and it is something that we need to be aware of. There have been rotating closures as a model, although we haven't found that really fitting for the communities we engage with. This form is not very acceptable by communities because people like to know where the closure is. And then everybody knows where the closure is, if you keep changing it, then people say, Oh, I didn't know the closure was there, or you change to it, and so on and so forth. But it's something to be aware of, for sure.

Andrew Wamukota 06:37

Thank you so much

Liz Drury O'Neill 06:38

Andrew, it is Liz online. I just want to add that I have a lot of data on incomes across different groups, and also the ecological side. But, it's perception data. So it's people's understanding and subjective perceptions of how they feel their income has gone up or gone down, or how they feel other people have benefited. And they also have a lot of descriptions, thick descriptions of how they felt the ecology has changed, or benefited from the closures, and especially on opening days as well. So we have the subjective side of what Lorna was talking about as well.

Tim Daw 07:22

But there was a perception of a positive impact on other fish species and octopus in your data.

Andrew Wamukota 07:29

Thank you Liz for clarifying that as well. So because of time, I think I would like us to wrap up this section and move [gap in the recording: Rose presented the invited panelists and start asking the questions]

Panel discussion (transcripts)

XX means we were not able to hear what was said in the recording.

Rose Mwaipopo

We have a strong panel and I believe that they will make a very good contribution to the OctoPINTS project and particularly to what that means to people. So, as we start this panel discussion I would

like to invite each panelist to briefly mention What is your freshest thought having heard the presentations and discussions so far?

Tanguy Nicolas 07:37

Thank you. A lot of thoughts, they were very rich presentations and I cannot wait to read some of the findings with more time from the papers. I found it very interesting how it articulates lots of factors that we deal with in conservation interventions, sometimes when it's about governance, there's so many factors involved, a lot of social factors, political factors, local to villages or island wider like in the case of Zanzibar and Pemba. And it's really interesting to see how it helps articulating some of these factors. So, we have lots of food for discussion I think.

Tahiry Randrianjafimanana 08:15

Thank you, for me, this research is really interesting and provides us some evidence and understanding about the closures and their success. And my comment is sometimes the community is motivated by the share of catch, but how is it with the cash? For example, it is like motivating the XX percent. Is it really for the community to be to lead also the success to continue it by organizing from themselves. Also, sometimes the community needs to be to understand what is working and not, and how also to make it successful in novel closures.

The second point is I like the method that this research used. Like story cycles, it is really important also to allow the community to be involved in the methods of the research. Because something like it is the right way that we also need to focus when we conduct research like that to make all people contribute and also to make them engage to XX the co-design of the research projects until also to find the result. Thank you.

Lorna Slade 09:53

Thank you. I don't know if we have any fisheries biologists here but I always think about our work as – If you're trying to understand fish behavior that's quite complicated. If you're trying to understand human behavior, I think that's a bit more complicated. But if you're trying to understand fishery behavior, that's the most complicated. And I think our job is probably one of the most critical ones. And that's not in a bad way. It's just that fishers I think, are very independent people, they have to make daily decisions on which their life and livelihoods depend. And I think some of the topics which the OctoPINTS project was looking at were a very important process to try and understand. So there's a very interesting project. Thanks.

Shauna Mahajan 10:48

So in my role at WWF, a lot of what I do is connecting how we learn and monitor at a local scale to a

national scale to a regional scale and to a global scale. So a lot of what resonated with me in the presentations was really some of the insights on the methods. And I think the dichotomy between the sort of inductive approaches, and the more indicator approaches left me with even more conviction that we really do need both when we're working across all these scales, and also the focus on how different people experience and perceive the changes and benefit or do not benefit from the closures. Also had me thinking about how we disaggregate impacts on people is something that we care more and more about. Conservation is how people are affected, and it helped me realize that even how people experience those changes will change throughout time, which poses another challenge for monitoring and research efforts.

Rose Mwaipopo 11:39

OK, thank you. Thank you very much. Probably let me start with you now. And since you've talked about your experience, and here we're talking about closures, from your own perspective, what would you say? Or what do you think, is a successful closure intervention? And probably, you can say, briefly, what do you think is or would lead to a successful outcome?

Shauna Mahajan 12:15

So I should start by saying that I'm sure everyone here in the room is more of an expert on closures than I am. But with that in mind, I think I mean, even reflecting on the presentations, I think, the more people who perceive benefits from them or not just receive benefits, but feel good about the closures, I really liked the focus on the fact that with each closures or when a closure opens, it's a celebratory event and recognizing the relational and social value of that. So I think the more we witness these positive social changes, I think that's a good indication that some of the rules and regulations that we theorize will have the impact we want them to be more successful over time.

Rose Mwaipopo 12:57

Thank you. Lorna. Could you add to that from your own perspective?

Lorna Slade 13:00

Just remind me what exactly what you want?

Rose Mwaipopo 13:02

From your own perspective, what would you say is successful? Successful outcome, successful outcome from the closure?

Lorna Slade 13:15

I think that ... and one of those sort of mantras in MWAMBAO is that ocean health is community

wealth. And I think success is an interesting thing to debate and talk about, because it means different things to different people. So if we have improved ocean health and community wealth in terms of not just money, but well-being, then I think that is an indicator of success. But I think, you know, I think success is an interesting thing. So when we might think that if we have more octopus and heavier octopus on the day of opening that success, but maybe what more influences the community in terms of practicing an intervention like this might be seeing the biggest octopus that they've ever seen in their life on the day of opening, you know, maybe that's the critical factor. That means success to them. So I think it's complex, I think complexity is the name of the game. Really.

Rose Mwaipopo 14:23

Thank you very much. And let me continue with Tahiry.

Tahiry Randrianjafimanana 14:27

Just, I want to add to the previous speaker, for me success depends on the community perspective. I really want to emphasize that the success likely what community wants to achieve is depending on our indicators, like ecological indicators, so the cash indicators like this one, but what community needs to want to achieve and XX, they want to make the point because sometimes they say okay, let's try with these closures because we want to be organized, or they want to move on the next management management measures, it depends on us on the community's needs, because that, or we Blue Ventures we try something like what's community needs? If it is the cash, okay, let's try with that. If the cash decline what happened, what do you want to achieve? What do they need to achieve? Sometimes like, okay, but for us, it's really important if you want, if we are mobilized, and also to be engaged in this management measure, it is also a good entry point to the global management of the fisheries. Thank you.

Rose Mwaipopo 15:37

Tanguy, do you want to add to that? I can give you, you can start with another question. Yeah. Okay.

Tanguy Nicolas 15:49

I just want to make it to take my conservation organization hat, I agree with what everyone has said so far. But yeah, success can also be about ecological aspects, which is not necessarily the point of view of the communities. It wouldn't be good to force the communities into that point of view. But from the conservation point of view, that can be also one of the aims of the closures. Not always the case. But it can be tricky.

Rose Mwaipopo 16:18

Thank you very much. Let me start with you now with a different question on research. Having heard

your colleagues and our presentations, from your own perspective, what kinds of research do you think can help us or can help you understand how to achieve this success that we're talking about? And you can also extend on whether you think, “process focused” or “indicator focused” research is important and why? So let's start with research. What kind of research do you think would help us understand?

Tanguy Nicolas 16:55

I tend to agree with what was said, I think in Tim's video presentation, that there is probably less qualitative and process focused research, than indicator quantitative to be quite caricature. And more needs to be done. And we can see that in the very quick overview of the results so far. It's really a lot of information to process, to digest and to communicate to all the stakeholders, from authorities to communities. So I think there is more need for that. But it's not to say that one is better than the other, I very much agree with Shauna that they need to be complementary. And I guess it's sometimes difficult to conduct this kind of research, it takes some specific skills, some specific experience, expertise, from the researchers, from the people working with the researchers. So it's not accessible to anyone. So it probably takes some capacity and training to conduct research.

Rose Mwaipopo 18:03

Thank you very much. Tahiry, with your experience, what do you think?

Tahiry Randrianjafimanana 18:06

Thanks for this question. From my perspective, definitely, I agree that research depends on the needs. And also it depends on the level of the questions that we need to answer. But for me, participatory research and evaluation is really needed. But not just to answer your research questions. But sometimes we should also integrate to the community-led process, within the research, and during the core design of the project research, and also for the dissemination of the research results, and also how the community being engaged also, in this dissemination, and also to address or to the community needs. So in summary, we have research, but we need to find a way that we conduct the research, participatory but also to address this research through community needs. Thank you.

Rose Mwaipopo 19:19

Thank you. Lorna with your work with MWAMBAAO.

Lorna Slade 19:26

Yeah, in MWAMBAAO we do both qualitative and quantitative research. I think it's not an either or I agree with it. With Shauna, we need to do both. I think working with fishers you realize, as I said, they're very independent people. It's very difficult. I mean, to get fishermen or fishers to agree to any

kind of closure or any kind of intervention is actually quite difficult. And everybody remembers a failure. So, you really want to put everything in place to aim for success the first time round, and you may not get another shot. That's the thing. So, we in MWAMBAO, we focus on informed governance, and management is based on evidence. We have a responsibility when we introduce any kind of intervention into the community. Therefore, I think we need to do all that we can to aim for success, the first time round includes knowing what we're talking about, and that it does succeed in an ecological sense. But also knowing that it will be as accepted as possible. Not everything is going to be accepted every time but at least you can collect the information and talk to people and understand what helps them to accept and not accept an intervention.

Rose Mwaipopo 21:01

Thank you. And if you could add, please Shauna.

Shauna Mahajan 21:05

I think just what you just said about the we only have one shot is offered only have one shot is a really important point. And I think it applies also to research. And so I think what I would add is that it's not just what we research, it's how we conduct research. And so I think there's a growing recognition of the importance of co-designing research. I know there's a session on that here this week. But I think oftentimes, we don't, we aren't clear as to what question we're trying to answer, even though we do have research questions. And we're not always clear as to who really needs to learn with us on that research process. So I think, in terms of what research is most useful, it's really taking the time to co-design and figure out who needs to learn with you. Because sometimes it is a simple, you know, three month quantitative study that will give you the answer you need. And sometimes it's a five year co-produce super complex, participatory research process and finding the right configuration of research, questions, goals, methods that are fit for purpose, I think, is what we all need a little more.

Rose Mwaipopo 22:08

Thank you. And before you leave the microphone, would you think these kinds of research, open ended research, are they useful to inform practical conservation?

Shauna Mahajan 22:22

I think yes, I think the pathway, or how it influences conservation practices is a little bit more complicated, I think something I see often is, we're very pressed for time in conservation organizations. And we don't always have time to sit and sort of ponder the meaning of life, which would be really nice and probably really good for our work. But the reality is, we work within these funding structures and pressures and demands from many different directions that few people have control over. And until we transform that system, we're still working, or so working fast. So I think it's I

think building relationships and having researchers who go after those bigger questions and, and kind of share that information in the right place at the right time can really help us as a field evolve, but it can't be all the research that we do.

Rose Mwaipopo 23:11

Thank you. Lorna, would you like to add?

Lorna Slade 23:14

Yes there is a funding implication as well too, so it's not just the time, funders want to see results, and they want to see numbers, they don't want to, you know, they're gonna be too happy with hearing 'we sat around the table for three months'. And, we came up with this baby. And so that is a constraint. I think as practitioners, some of the methodologies that Liz used in her research were very valuable. I think we can use those methodologies. And we need to get better as practitioners, to use those kinds of methodologies to really dig into why things go well, or why they don't go well, to learn so that we can sort of have an adaptive management cycle. And therefore, I think it is very difficult when you have a fund and you have a work plan, and you're doing ABC and you've got to get that done by month three, to then sit back and say, Okay, well, this perhaps could have gone better. We need another month to do that. But I think we need to, perhaps be brave enough to demand that time when we need it. Because if you don't take the people with you on these journeys, then you're not going to get there in the end. Thank you.

Rose Mwaipopo 24:35

Thank you. Let me just ask you from a different angle. Conservation is of course, one of the ultimate goals that we would want, success. But one of the things that we would like to probably associate with success is empowering the community. And how would you say that you associate the power in the community and having a successful outcome, let's say of conservation, from your experience is empowering the community an important goal or eventually it is conservation?

Tahiry Randrianjafimanana 25:11

Do you mean that the outcome of the closure success? Yeah, yeah, as I said earlier, but it depends on the community, what it needs. But, sometimes the community says, okay, like, our outcome is the cash. So, sometimes the ecological, but sometimes they say, Okay, let's organize ourselves through these octopus closures. So, we can go with that first. And when they have some, some success on the cash, it's okay, when we are well organized. We said go ahead with God. So I think the first one who is we should listen to the community, what they need, and then try also to plan with them. If we can do that, we can also do some monitoring to track change. And then we can accompany the community with this progression of for example the closure, because with the community, we have a

documented community progress. For example, the first thing is to have the closures, and to have the engagement with that. Next, okay, if we were engaged with these closures, let's find other ones, and so on. And to see the progression of the community with this success of engagement.

Rose Mwaipopo 26:47

Thank you. Tanguy, if you would like to talk about community empowerment.

Tanguy Nicolas 26:55

So if you can remind me, the question is how do I think community empowerment can be a success?

Rose Mwaipopo 27:03

Yeah, I mean, how is it associated with a successful outcome?

Tanguy Nicolas 27:07

Yeah, because empowerment is also quite some broad words and can mean various things, and thus various forms of empowerment. I agree with what the others have just said. It can be a journey, where you see the community members individually feeling that they gain from various kinds of gains, for instance relational gains, as it's been flagged in the presentation, economic gains, and ecological gains. So, that can be a form of empowerment, but also in the way they discuss with the various authorities, the fisheries department, in the MPA management. So, having some form of recognition from these various stakeholders from the traders as well, at various levels, and the way they are viewed by the stakeholders, or they're perceived as they are viewed, I think that configures an empowerment as well. So yes, definitely.

Rose Mwaipopo 28:05

Thank you. Thank you very much to the panelists. And Andrew, chairperson, can we, I would like to open the question, a very small question to the audience. I want to thank the panelists. Could you join me in a round of applause? Thank you very much. But, before you leave, I would like to ask the question. We've presented our research, presented our findings, of course it is ongoing, probably there could be something that one of us would like to add. Is there any angle, any methodology, any approach that you would like to add that we haven't highlighted so far? And the thing that would be important in all of these ideas on closures, communities, and everything about successful outcomes, please feel free to contribute, we have a few minutes to go. So we can start with you. If there's anything that you think is important, that you haven't highlighted so far? And could you add please, anybody, it is free. And then, anybody from the community is welcome.

Tahiry Randrianjafimanana 29:21

So, I just want to highlight that, when you have a question, research is really useful, like this one. And just that we need to make sure that the question is really clear. And the output of the research that we need, we want to achieve, because sometimes when we conduct research, and the way we have the simple question, we want to watch what and with our methods, like a scientific method, that it's not really simple. We make it difficult by focusing on details and sometimes it takes time. But you know, sometimes we need a supportive community to take action, because of our methods. It is really complicated, or the question is really simple. So let's try with that. This way, like we have the questions, who is asking questions? who is answering? What do we need to see with this question? If it is simple, go ahead with our simple method, before being conducted by communities, and to see what the finding is, and we take action with that. And if the question is really difficult, we also take the appropriate methods, maybe test them, and then when we have the finding, we translate into operational. This is what I want to emphasize because sometimes we have an easy question, but sometimes it's not, not really not easy for but it's not clear. But sometimes also, it is simple. So we may use also the simple method, not the complicated method.

Rose Mwaipopo 31:03

Thank you. And if I just want to ask, making it simpler to the communities that we engage with. Thank you very much. Lorna, would you want to add?

Lorna Slade 31:13

If I understood you correctly, you just want some reflections or something to add. Right. I think there's a question about this kind of research and who should do it? You know, should it be the organization that's implementing this kind of research? Should it be people from outside? Should it be independent? If the organization is involved, you know, does that not make it impartial? These are interesting questions. I think, from my perspective, if you engage in your work in a participatory way, then I think, using some of these methods to dig a bit deeper into why things worked, or what didn't work. People are going to trust you if you've already built that relationship. And therefore I feel that implementing organizations should use these, you know, carry out their own research, maybe we don't call it research, we just call it sort of a follow on and finding out why things were successful or not successful or how we could improve next time. So collaborative learning, I would say, I think we need to engage in that. Thank you.

Shauna Mahajan 32:33

I think one thing that I have been thinking a lot about lately is how it's sort of on the lines of what you were just saying is how do we do this more collaborative research between, you know, I speak from the NGO perspective and academia. And I think, for researchers to take a little more time to understand the context in which decisions are being made and projects are being planned within

NGOs. If NGOs are the primary users of the knowledge, it may not be the case, it may be that communities directly or the government, but it really takes time. And it depends on trust, to understand that decision-making context and in that way, recommendations for what actions that might improve outcomes could be better co-designed between researchers and NGOs. Because I do think researchers bring a really valuable perspective, they're able to take a lot more time to think deeply about questions and offer this sort of outsider's perspective, but kind of going through that process more collaboratively with other stakeholders can help, I think, to get to new ideas for actions that could improve outcomes.

Rose Mwaipopo 33:41

Thank you very much. Anybody from the audience? Okay, Andrew, do you want to say something?

Audience responses to the session (transcripts)

Andrew Wamukota 33:52

Thank you for that Rose. So, maybe we can just finish this so that when you get up, we don't have to go and sit down again. But there's one thing that I would like to ask, maybe as the panelist or the audience, what is that one thing that you will take home from this mini symposium, which looks at slightly different kinds of research approaches, but is that one thing that you think you can take home from this?

Speaker 1 34:46

When there's better inclusion or participation of communities from the start of a project, then that somewhat guarantees its success.

Andrew Wamukota 34:56

Okay. Thank you so much for that. Please go ahead Speaker 4.

Speaker 4 35:10

For me, I would say the difference between consent and compliance. So, when you're making rules, let's say, when you're talking about octopus closures, seasonal closing, and all that we need to get to a point where communities are agreeing to what you want to do and not imposing it on them.

Liz Drury O'Neill 35:32

However, you're never going to have a full agreement.

Speaker 5 35:35

It's practically the same thing Speaker 4 said. I think using words that resonate with communities, if they feel the word should be consent, work with consent. And I think the approach to take is, listen more and work together.

Andrew Wamukota 35:55

Thank you so much for that. We have one more hand here. Yes, please.

Speaker 6 36:02

Speaker from CORDIO. And, I'm looking at research as a learning process. And when she says, clarifying the question, and recognizing who do we need to learn with? Who are we working with this journey, so that you're not just ticking some boxes of our research? Thank you.

Andrew Wamukota 36:22

Thanks. There's two more hands here.

Speaker 7 36:30

Yeah, I was just thinking how powerful the model that we saw was, and how amazing it would be if we could try and combine those two methodologies more. So the model was using perception data, or somehow it was more participatory, so that we could use it to predict potentially what was going to happen with the effects of climate change. Or maybe we could look at the interaction of gender and uses of the resources and use it more in a participatory way. Maybe in terms of predicting into the future, or just understanding the situation right now.

Andrew Wamukota 37:10

Thanks, thanks for that. I hope that the Stockholm team, you're able to follow?

Tim Daw 37:19

Yes, thank you very much, Andrew. And thanks very much. We were just expressing our gratitude to the panelists and the audience members for sharing your reflections.

Andrew Wamukota 37:29

So, Tim, before that, there's one more question from the audience or contribution, and then allow Emilie to share on the modeling, the agent-based modeling question. And then, I'll give you an opportunity to make your final remarks before we close.

Speaker 8 37:52

Yeah, thank you. I really appreciate you coming to the presentation of the successfulness of closures, it's really important to have to listen to the community. Because when we talk about closures, policymakers, at the local level, local authorities, and communities, XX in the market have different interpretations of closures, and it's really important to take that into account. What the stakeholders' vision of, of the aim of the closure, so, really appreciate that. Thanks.

Andrew Wamukota 38:38

Thank you so much. That was very useful feedback from the participants. So I would like to give Emilie, if you can hear us maybe one minute or less.

Emilie Lindkvist 38:50

Yeah! Thanks, Andrew. And thanks for reflecting on the modeling possibilities. So, I think that what was raised is something that we're really working on and trying to do. We have a lot of perceptions data in the model. So it's built in this qualitative approach to modeling. So trying to bring that in, and the participatory approach - it's hard to know how to do that in the best way now that we're ending the project. The scenarios that I showed are something that we're still developing. Which ones should we present and how should we do that? And so I would love to follow up with any of you who's interested in having an online question of which one scenario are you more interested in exploring and how can we do that together? That would be amazing. We have a website that if you just google OctoPINTS, then it should come up. It's a WordPress site. So you can maybe connect through there. Or, yeah, try to find us online. But, it may be possible to sign up with Andrew or, or Rose before you leave as well, if you're not already getting our information, you are already on our email list. And so also adding a big, big thank you to the audience and the panelists and Rose and Andrew, to so professionally hosted this session in place, it's been very, very good, and maybe to hand it over to Tim, do you want to add something?

Tim Daw 40:58

Just to echo what Emilie said, I think, lots of interesting reflections. I mean, just some of the reflections that were popping up amongst the team here about sort of reflecting on the diversity of the views within we use the word community a lot. And what Rose was pointing out in terms of the negotiation of quite different perspectives, even within a certain what we might class as a group of stakeholders. And that process of active negotiation. And I think another thing that we took away was this sort of understanding the context, as researchers understand not just understanding the context of our of a particular closure or a system or a community, but also understanding the context, the decision making context, as Shauna put it, of the of the different organizations who are partners within the research as being a really useful pointer for academic research doing collaborations. Thanks very much.

Andrew Wamukota 42:07

Thanks, thank you very much, Tim and Emilie, and the Stockholm team for joining us virtually, I would like to thank the panelists for as well as the audience, on behalf of myself, and on behalf of the OctoPINTS team, for that very wonderful and fruitful engagement, discussing about the subject of closures. It is my hope, and the hope of the OctoPINTS team, that this is just a continuation of the beginning of continuation of the WIO networking on the closure subject through for like this and others, and indeed, other subjects that we may be interested in that are related to the same. So thank you so much for joining us. You are free to sign to the OctoPINTS through me and Rose. You can visit the website so that we can have a continuation of this discussion.

Transcribed by <https://otter.ai> - cleaned by Jineth Berrío-Martínez and edited further by Emilie Lindkvist.

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